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Librarians' Level of Awareness and Perception of Artificial Intelligence and Robotics in Federal University Libraries in Southeast, Nigeria

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Abstract

Librarians' level of awareness and perception of AI and robotics are paramount in determining their applications and utilization in any library. This study therefore aimed at determining librarians' level of awareness and perception of artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design and was guided by three research questions. The population sample of the study was 50 librarians drawn from 5 federal university libraries in Southeast Nigeria, selected through a random sampling technique with the aid of research assistants from each of the universities, while a Likert four-point type structured questionnaire was the only instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Measurement and Evaluation of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Nigeria, using Cronbach's alpha. Results showed a coefficient of $\alpha=.84$. The questionnaires were sent through respondents' emails and were also returned through the same channel 100%. Data collected were analyzed using frequencies and simple percentile and presented in tables. The findings revealed that librarians' level of awareness of AI and its tools was very low. Regardless, they had a positive perception of the usefulness of the

application and utilization of AI in university libraries in Southeast Nigeria, but they also perceived it as a technology that would have an adverse effect on library staff and information utilization. It was based on the findings that the study recommended, among other things, that librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria in particular and Nigeria, in general, should not wait to be reminded to now tailor their efforts towards acquiring AI skills by training and retraining as to be prepared to face the challenges when the technology is finally introduced in their libraries and also to remain relevant in the scheme of things.

Keywords: University library, Librarian, Perception, Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Robots

1.0. Introduction

The world, with much excitement, heralded and continued to celebrate the emergence of ICT, a technological invention powered by the computer, an invention that delved into every aspect of human activities that the world today is ruled by information and communication technology. With the euphoria and gains of the ICT range, the world in the last 20 years has once again witnessed another technological invention powered by the computer. This time, artificial intelligence (AI), though nothing new at this point, is one of the most impactful technologies the business world has ever seen. Artificial intelligence is the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems (TechTarget, 2024).is making education faster and more efficient. It is breaking the paradigms of the past on how to learn. AI is a positive force for good in the world. AI is important because of its potential to change how we live, work, and play. It has been effectively used in business to automate tasks done by humans, including customer service work, lead generation, fraud detection and quality control. In a number of areas, AI can perform tasks much better than humans. Particularly when it comes to repetitive, detail-oriented tasks, such as analyzing large numbers of legal documents to ensure relevant fields are filled in properly, AI tools often complete jobs quickly and with relatively few_errors. This transformative technology, powered by machine learning algorithms and data analytics, is completely changing the research landscape. With the aid of AI, researchers can process vast amounts of data, extract meaningful insights, and automate repetitive tasks (Abbadia, 2023).

Indeed, AI has the potential to speed up the pace of scientific discovery and enhance the quality of research outcomes. In fact, AI has brought about notable changes to academia, revolutionizing the way research is conducted, knowledge is generated, and education is delivered.

On the part of the library, it is noted that the emergence of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has brought an undeniable transformation in library operations and the ways services are provided to users and other stakeholders, and the inclusion of ICT facilities in the management of the library has tremendous positive effect in the management of the library (Onwubiko, 2022) as it has taken hold of almost every aspect of human activities even in some cases, doing better what the human cannot do. The belief is that AI has the potential to change how we live, work and play. It has been effectively used in business to automate tasks done by humans, including customer service work, lead generation, fraud detection and quality control. In a number of areas, AI can perform tasks much better than humans. Particularly when it comes to repetitive, detail-oriented tasks, such as analyzing large numbers of legal documents to ensure relevant fields are filled in properly, AI tools often complete jobs quickly and with relatively few errors (TechTarget, 2024) Furthermore, the assertion is that AI also holds significant potential in the dissemination of information.

Libraries, especially university libraries, are not left out in the phenomenal transformation. The belief among academic librarians and academic information managers, especially those of developed nations, which may not be far from the truth, is that the rapid advancements in AI and robotics have brought about transformative changes across various industries, and academic libraries should not be the exception. University Libraries serve as information hubs fostering learning, research and community engagement. Integrating AI and robotics into library services, therefore, has the potential to enhance user experience and expand access to information in innovative ways. The bottom line is that university libraries are specifically established to support the tripartite functions of learning, teaching and research in their various parent institutions (Onwubiko, 2020). To this end, AI is envisaged as a good tool for enhancing effective service delivery to academic researchers and other users. The rapid advancements in AI and robotics

have brought about transformative changes across various industries, and the field of library services is no exception. Libraries serve as information hubs fostering learning, research and community engagement. Integrating AI and robotics into library services has the potential to enhance user experience and expand access to information in innovative ways (Abbadia, 2023).

The assertion is that Artificial intelligence (AI) has demonstrated the capacity to promote knowledge acquisition across all levels and programmes of the millennium education system. Among the areas in which AI has made marks are, though not limited to, Medicine, Engineering, Education, and Marketing sciences. Recently, marketing practices have been using AI to perform all sorts of sophisticated and less sophisticated electronic transactions. It is obvious that there is still limited or a lack of scholarly research in this area when it comes to libraries in developing countries like Nigeria. However, there are emerging examples of libraries exploring the potential of AI, such as the US Library of Congress' LC Labs (Haffenden et al., 2023). This, therefore, has placed serious demand on libraries, especially academic libraries and librarians in Nigerian universities, to include electronic marketing in their services and also expose the students to acquire knowledge and skills via educational AI technologies. Inasmuch as this technology is being celebrated in developed nations because of its positive contributions in various fields and complimenting certain human activities, it is in doubt whether to the best knowledge of the researcher if there is any university library in Southeast, Nigeria in particular and Nigeria as a whole that has applied the services of AI. It is against this backdrop that this study became necessary and aimed at ascertaining librarians' level of awareness and perception of AI in university libraries with a special focus on federal university libraries in Southeast, Nigeria

The principal objectives of this study, therefore, are,

- i. To ascertain librarians in Federal universities in Southeast Nigeria level of awareness of AI and other related tools
- ii. To determine the Librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria's perception of the application and utilization of AI in university libraries
- iii. To ascertain whether Librarians perceived likely adverse effects of the application and utilization of AI and robotics in university libraries in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria

1.2. Research Questions

This study is guided by the following three research questions:

- i. To what extent are librarians in federal university libraries in Southeast Nigeria aware of the existence of AI and related tools?
- ii. What perception do librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria have of AI applications and utilizations in university libraries?
- iii. What are the perceived likely adverse effects of the application and utilization of AI and robotics on university libraries in a federal university in Southeast Nigeria?

2.0. Literature review

2.1. Conceptual Framework

2.1.1. Perception

The term perception is a noun and has its etymology from the Latin word 'perception', meaning comprehension, which is, according to Wikipedia (2008), the process of attaining awareness or understanding of sensory information. At the same time, the Collins Essential English Dictionary (2006) describes it as insight or intuition and a way of viewing. Merriam-Webster (n.d.a) lists these definitions: "1 a: a result of observation; b: a mental image; 2. obsolete: consciousness; 3 a: awareness of the elements of environment through physical sensation; b: physical sensation interpreted in the light of experience; 4 a: quick, acute, and intuitive cognition appreciation; b: a capacity for comprehension." The Merriam-Webster Online Thesaurus (2009) adds this: "1. the ability to understand inner qualities or relationships; 2. the knowledge gained from the process of coming to know or understand something." Synonyms in Roget's II: The New Thesaurus (1995) include awareness, cognizance, consciousness, sense, concept, conception, idea, image, notion, and thought. Other related terms are attention, cognition, heuristic, information, intelligence, mental model, and understanding (Wikipedia, 2008).

According to Lumen (n.d), perception refers to the way sensory information is organized, interpreted, and consciously experienced. Perception involves both bottom-up and top-down processing. Bottom-up processing refers to the fact that perceptions are built from sensory input. On the other hand, how we interpret those sensations is influenced by our available knowledge, our experiences, and our thoughts. This is called top-down processing. Cherry (2020) explained that perception is the sensory experience of the world. It involves both recognizing environmental stimuli and actions in response to these stimuli. Through the perceptual process, we gain information about the properties and elements of the environment that are critical to our survival. Perception not only creates our experience of the world around us; it allows us to act within our environment. Perception is a uniquely individualized experience. One can only draw from what is known to oneself, just as in the analogy of the blind man and the elephant. The conclusion that can be drawn is that perception is a multifaceted concept that is as complex as the human mind itself (Onwubiko, 2022).

2.1.2. Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is an important sub-discipline of computer science. It was first defined during the Dartmouth Conference in 1956 as a technology that can research, develop and create a "brain of machine" that is akin to that of humans and enables machines to think and learn like humans (Nick, 2017). With the rapid development of science and technology, AI is getting more mature and has been applied in every industry or trade. More specifically, it has reshaped and dramatically changed the patterns and ways of information dissemination. Artificial intelligence technology, no doubt, is redefining the modes of information dissemination. In this regard, Artificial intelligence has been defined as the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems with specific applications to include expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition and machine vision (Tech target, 2023)

On the other hand, as the hype around AI accelerates, vendors are now scrambling to promote how their products and services use it. Often, what they refer to as AI is simply a component of the technology, such as machine learning. AI requires a foundation of

specialized hardware and software for writing and training machine learning algorithms. No single programming language is synonymous with AI, but Python, R, Java, C++, and Julia have features that are popular with AI developers. In general, AI systems work by ingesting large amounts of labelled training data, analyzing the data for correlations and patterns, and using these patterns to make predictions about future states. In this way, a chatbot that is fed examples of text can learn to generate lifelike exchanges with people, or an image recognition tool can learn to identify and describe objects in images by reviewing millions of examples. New, rapidly improving generative AI techniques can create realistic text, images, music and other media. All in all, AI programming focuses on cognitive skills that include the following: learning, reasoning, self-correction and creativity (Chen & Wu Han, 2022). For the sake of clarity, chatbots are often referred to as virtual assistants or digital assistants, and they are much more sophisticated, interactive, and personalized than task-oriented chatbots. These chatbots are contextually aware and leverage natural-language understanding (NLU), NLP, and ML to learn as they go. They apply predictive intelligence and analytics to enable personalization based on user profiles and past user behaviour. Digital assistants can learn a user's preferences over time, provide recommendations, and even anticipate needs. In addition to monitoring data and intent, they can initiate conversations.

2.1.3. Robotics and Robots

Robotics and Artificial Intelligence are two terms that are often confused and sometimes not distinguished, but they actually refer to different technologies. Artificial intelligence is a discipline that focuses on enabling machines to develop the same intellectual capabilities as humans. Robotics, on the other hand, is the science of designing and building physical robots to improve automation and innovation. Suffice it to say that robotics and AI are two related fields of science and technology, but they have several differences. Robotics is the discipline that deals with designing machines capable of automating tasks. Robotics experts also create, programme and operate these automated elements to develop certain skills and tasks. Imperatively, Robotics focuses on the manipulation of the physical area, unlike AI, which is oriented towards the internal or digital part (Laskowski & Tucci, 2024). In other words, Robotics is the branch of engineering and computer sciences where machines are built to perform programmed tasks without further human intervention. Robotics, therefore, creates machines that have their own mobility and can interact with the environment

and are generally used to perform repetitive, high-speed or high-precision tasks, e.g. in industrial sectors of chain production or in the field of medicine. Simply put, robotics is where robots are built and programmed to perform very specific duties. (Telefonica, 2023)

Generally, both robotics and AI aim to automate tasks and facilitate human processes, as well as utilize data collected by input and output sensors to facilitate decision-making. In this sense, it is increasingly common to see work environments where machines collaborate with people to improve different tasks. This human-machine collaboration is embodied in cobots or collaborative robots, which are specifically designed to perform tedious tasks that require greater effort. Their applications are useful in almost any sector, and they are gradually being adapted to different environments (Martin, 2021).

In a nutshell, this field of engineering focuses on the design and manufacturing of robots. While designed, robots are often used to perform tasks that are difficult for humans to perform or perform consistently. For instance, robots are used in car production assembly lines and by NASA to move large objects in space. Researchers also use machine learning to build robots that can interact in social settings (TechTarget, 2023)

2.2. Theoretical and Empirical Studies on AI and Academic Libraries

When it comes to transformation and information management, libraries, especially university libraries, are at the forefront as they are seen as research hubs and custodians of knowledge spearheaded by information. In this context, the emergence of AI in the past two decades has posed another responsibility on the libraries, considering the fact that they must not be left behind in the trends of modern information management and dissemination mechanisms if they are to remain relevant in the comity of professional and technological transformation more so those powered by computer the mother of ICT.

However, recent empirical studies carried out by Farag et al. (2021) with respect to AI and its applications and usability in academic libraries discovered a weak understanding of artificial intelligence among most library workers, with 69% saying they do not use AI. The study also found that AI is currently being used in indexing, analysis, retrieval, storage, photography, and meeting the needs of library users. However, there is a lack of training for workers in the AI sector, which is attributed to the lack of training courses. The study concludes that AI should be used as an assistive technology for library specialists but not relied on entirely. The main challenges faced by academic libraries are a lack of physical equipment, limited local AI technology suppliers, and a lack of experience of researchers and students in dealing with technological innovations. In the same vein, Weijia (2022), in his study, identify that the primary elements influencing a library's preparation for AI include leadership focus, experience with AI applications, acceptance of AI, awareness of AI, and the innovation environment and therefore suggests that library administrators must be abreast of the most recent technical developments in the industry, routinely evaluate their library's readiness for AI, and swiftly install AI technologies.

To this end, the assertion is that it has become imperative for libraries, especially university libraries, to embrace this new technological invention called artificial intelligence (AI) to enhance their roles as information managers and drivers of access to knowledge. AI and its related tools are seen as veritable instruments for re-positioning university libraries with a view to taking the accrued advantages offered by AI in refining the quality of services delivered in this era in which the growth of information is in astronomical rate weighing down librarians and libraries as not to efficiently and effectively meet up with information needs of their teeming clientele nor share information among themselves. As expressed by Mogali, (2015), the application of AI can aid the library to integrate data sets with other libraries and institutions to create a seamless exchange of data and research across sectors and disciplines. AI can take on stressful and complex work that humans may struggle cannot do, it also completes tasks faster than a human can most likely

The inclusion of AI and AI tools in academic libraries noted Vijayakumar & Sheshadri (2019) will bring a turnaround in academic library services and management as it will spur information technology connectivity and also actively support information usage as well as easing clients' search and immediately address their needs. The impact of artificial intelligence and advanced computer technology on the nature of future libraries will be enormous and the quality difference varies from experts. Other highlighted areas AI tools can be on immense benefit to the university libraries as it concerns library services management and delivery which include circulation services, shelving of books, cataloguing of library materials, among others. Many academic libraries, most especially those in the developed countries make use of AI for the provision of library services to the users (Asefeh and Asemi, 2018).

Furtherance, it has been noticed that AI implementation can reduce human errors and inefficiencies, since there would be less redundancy and error free operations the library can satisfy the needs of the users even without meeting them physically. This will also allow librarians to focus on more important tasks like developing the library collections, the research sections etc. They aim to simulate human intelligence with computers. Vijayakumar & Sheshadri (2019) talked about the Artificial Intelligent sub areas such as expert systems, natural language processing, pattern recognition and robotics. As they explained, the Expert System is a computerized knowledge system that serves as an interface or gateway for providing access to the database and obtaining relevant information, while, the ultimate generation of computer language is Natural Language in that computer can understand the key language concepts within a question and solution through the natural language process. It aims to design and create a computer that analyzes the language that a person uses, understands and generates. Speech synthesis, machine translation, linguistic approaches, information recovery, information extraction and speech recognition are the various elements of natural language processing. Whereas, Components for pattern recognition are data collection, pre-processing, selection of characters, selection of models, training and evaluation and robotics as AI subfield, which deals with motor and perceptive tasks. Robot is a mechanical device which carries out automation tasks using artificial intelligence techniques, either directly human control or a predetermined program. AI can also be applied in libraries to create programs for successful reference services, textbook scanning, and the identification of relevant subject groups. Furthermore,

AI technology can help library users find library content by using intelligent tutoring systems and automated library services. As a result, AI acceptance and application in libraries will enable better information processing as well as better information search, which will thrill both library workers and users because information will be easier and faster to obtain.

On the hand, the invention of AI technology has also its ugly side to the world as a whole and to the academic libraries in particular. The fact that academic libraries are still basking in the euphoria of the tremendous transformation brought about by the automation of libraries as a result of the emergence of ICT there is therefore this thunderous calls for the exploration of AI technology by Libraries. In the contrary, there is this school of thought that believes that it applications in the libraries will be a wind that may turn to tsunami regardless of the fact that most libraries especially those of the developing nations like Nigeria are currently battling operational inefficiency, technical disadvantage, challenges keeping their present audience and attracting new ones, and more and this regards Korinex and Stiglitz (2017) maintained that advances in AI technologies might bring about job loss or job polarization.

Echedom & Okuonghae (2021) in their explore the potential and limitations of using artificial intelligence (AI) in academic libraries in Africa observed though that AI has the potential to significantly improve information services and provide a new level of efficiency but there are still challenges, such as inadequate infrastructure and a lack of proper training. While Yoon et al. (2022) conducted a survey to learn about the opinions of North American librarians regarding the use of AI and associated technologies in libraries and found favourable perception of these technologies among academic and public librarians and also discovered, that 21% of librarians were already utilizing AI and related technologies and showed intense curiosity about these technologies and similar perspectives on whether AI is appropriate for various library tasks.

Bradley's (2022) article explores the topic of AI ethics and usage in libraries. The author highlights how libraries are involved in AI's regulatory advancements. The study also discusses how libraries have contributed to creating ethical frameworks and how their

operations are represented in national AI initiatives. Despite libraries' scant inclusion in current AI initiatives, the industry actively participates in consultations to guarantee an ethical and open future for AI. Because AI legislation is still in its infancy, the author contends there is still potential for libraries to participate. While Borgohain et al. (2022) conducted a bibliometric analysis of studies in AI from 2012 through 2021 and discovered that there wasn't as much study on AI applications in libraries compared to other fields like medicine, education, agriculture, and health. Price's law indicated that this industry saw exponential expansion. The most well-liked study topics were machine learning, deep learning, big data, and high-level programming languages. The authors concluded that AI technology might significantly enhance the current information system.

Panda and Chakravarty (2022) in a study through the utilization of Engati, a versatile AI chatbot service, to provide an overview of its uses and multitasking features in libraries found that AI chatbots offer a reliable solution for initiating virtual assistance, augmenting reference services, and promoting a "library without walls" concept. The study emphasizes the integration of AI with other technologies and its impact on intelligent information services, emphasizing the need for libraries to consider implementing AI-enabled chatbots as virtual assistants to meet user information needs. The study further revealed that chatbots can improve service quality, personalization, engagement, automation, revenue generation, and user satisfaction in libraries, serving as a valuable marketing tool and enhancing information literacy. In his study Liu et al. (2022) on the application of artificial intelligence (AI) technology in the information retrieval of university libraries did reveal that the main problems in AI information retrieval technology for university libraries included inadequate understanding of natural language, unclear knowledge representation, and difficulty in acquiring knowledge. Ali et al. (2022) in their study on incorporating AI in Pakistani university libraries discovered that although librarians knew AI's potential advantages in delivering cutting-edge services and enhancing user experience, they also voiced reservations about the expense and resources needed to adopt AI. The study employed a SWOT analysis to determine the advantages, disadvantages, opportunities, and risks related to the deployment of AI. The findings indicated a sluggish adoption of AI technology by Pakistani university libraries' administration, but financial, infrastructural, and technical talent issues remain and must be resolved.

While another survey on the opinions of academic library directors in Hungary about the application of AI in libraries was carried out by Winkler and Kiszl in 2022. According to the findings, most library directors regard AI as an opportunity rather than a threat. It might help with various library operations, including digitization, information service, and education. Information retrieval and data processing solutions backed by AI were found to be used by 25% of the libraries surveyed. Virtual or online services, reference services, and digitization have been deemed the domains where AI support was most appropriate. The outcomes are consistent with global patterns and imply that library directors are knowledgeable about using AI in libraries.

Gasparini and Kautonen (2022) in their study discovered a range of viewpoints among libraries and librarians towards AI, with some welcoming the technology and others worried about its potential to undermine human values. Inasmuch as the author through the review, discovered how libraries successfully apply design methodologies to handle AI-related difficulties, they also exposed crucial challenges like ethical transparency and the place of AI as a standalone entity. The authors suggest using design to address upcoming issues and generate opportunities. The interaction between libraries and stakeholders is also considered crucial. A study on the applications of AI in Taiwanese university libraries by Huang (2022) revealed that the librarians' had positive views towards the use of AI but require more in-depth information and organizational activities surrounding AI.

3.0. Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design with a sampled population of 50 librarians (20 male and 30 female) derived from five federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria; Alex Ekwueme federal university, Ikwo, Ebonyi State, Federal University technology, Owerri, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka (NAU) and University of Nigeria, Nsukka (UNN) with each university producing 10 respondents that are all certified librarians while the study was guided

	enhancing image quality and details	*	*	*	*	7	14	43	86	1.14
7	ChatGPT: AI model for natural language processing and generating human-like text responses	12	24	17	34	7	14	14	28	2.54
8	Generative AI - The use of AI to create new content, like text, images, music, audio, and videos.	8	16	27	54	6	12	9	18	2.68
9	Lovo.ai: Lovo.ai has garnered accolades as an award-winning voice generator and text-to-speech solution.	*	*	5	10	17	34	28	56	1.54
10	Reply.io: Reply offers a comprehensive sales engagement platform that enables the scalable creation of new opportunities while ensuring a personalized touch in every interaction.	2	4	7	14	9	18	32	64	1.58

Key: VHE=Very High Extent; HE= High Extent; LE= Low Extent; VLE = Very Low Extent Significant mean benchmark=2.50

The data in table 1 above reveal the level of awareness of librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria of AI and its tools. The data did show that of the 10 items in the table, only four which are, artificial intelligence, robotics and robots, ChatGPT and generative AI crossed the significant mean benchmark of 2.50 in which case the data show that 100% of the respondents are aware of the existence of AI, robotics and robots and between 60 and 70% are aware of ChatGPT and generative AI while the remaining were below or indicate that over 80% of the respondents have little or no knowledge of the various AI tools. An indication that most of the AI tools were unknown to the librarians or that their level of aware was to a very low extent.

What perception do librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria have of AI applications and utilizations of AI in university libraries?

Table 2: Librarians in federal universities in Southeast perception of the application and utilization of AI in university libraries

	SA	A	DA	SDA	
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Item	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	Mean
AI can be used to develop personalized recommendation systems that suggest relevant materials based on user preference and behavior	21	42	19	38	10	20			3.42
Robots can be used for shelving	31	62	18	36	*	*	1	2	3.58
Robots can be used for inventory management and maintenance	24	48	24	48	2	4	*	*	3.44
Robots can be used for data analytics for collection development	15	30	17	34	6	12	12	24	2.7
Utilizing AI-driven data analytics to assess user trends, preference and demands, thereby informing collection development strategies	38	76	12	24	*	*	*	*	3.76
It will enhance information accessibility as AI and robotics will make library services more accessible for both able and disabled individuals, including text-to-speech, sign language interpretation and navigation assistance.	19	38	23	46	6	12	2	4	3.18
Use of AI will promote digital preservation and archiving	50	100	*	*	*	*	*	*	4.00
Exploring the role of AI-powered Chatbots and virtual assistants will enhance the provision of instant customer support, answering queries and assisting with information retrieval	32	64	18	36	*	*	*	*	3.64
Robots can be used to perform library technical jobs like classification, shelving and selection of information materials	27	54	17	34	1	2	5	10	3.32

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree Significant mean benchmark=2.50

Table 2 displays data on librarians' awareness and perception of the application and utilization of AI and its tools in university libraries. The data show all the items in table 2 crossed the benchmark of 2.50 which indicates that over 80% of the respondents to a high extent are aware of the usefulness of the application and utilization of AI in university libraries as well as have positive perception towards its applications and utilization.

What are the perceived likely adverse effect of application and utilization of AI and robotics on university libraries in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria?

Table 3: Librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria perceived likely adverse effect of application and utilization of AI and robotics in university libraries

S/No	Item	SA		A		DA		SDA		Mean
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
1	AI can affect ethical issues and risks surrounding data privacy	27	54	23	46	*	*	*	*	3.48
2	Endangers security	17	34	13	26	12	24	8	16	2.78
3	Misinformation and bias	50	100	*	*	*	*	*	*	4.00
4	It can promote plagiarism,	50	100	*	*	*	*	*	*	4.00
5	Copyright infringements and harmful content.	50	100	*	*	*	*	*	*	4.00
6	AI lack of transparency	25	50	13	26	9	18	3	6	3.26
7	AI has the potential for worker displacement	21	42	13	26	7	14	9	18	2.92
8	librarians might start to think that AI knows everything and can replace human search	32	64	9	18	3	6	6	12	3.22
9	Librarians might start relying too much on AI and forget to think for themselves	32	64	9	18	3	6	6	12	3.22

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, DA=Disagree, SDA=Strongly Disagree Significant mean benchmark=2.50

As shown in table 3, the data indicate that librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria strongly agree that application of AI in university libraries will have adverse effect majorly on librarians and utilization of information by the general public. The data show that all the 9 items in the table crossed the acceptance significant mean benchmark of 2.50 which shows that over 70% of the

respondents strongly agree or agree that all the listed items are likely adverse effect application of AI in university libraries will have on both the librarians and information utilization.

Discussion of Results

The outcome of this study as shown in table 1, did show that librarians in federal universities in Southeast Nigeria apart from being to a very high extent aware of the existence of AI, robotics and robots and to a high extent ChatGPT and generative AI have little or no knowledge of most of the AI related tools. This result collaborates the finding of Farag et al. (2021) who in their study on AI and its applications and the usability in academic library discovered a weak understanding of artificial intelligence among most library workers, with 69% saying they do not use AI.

The perception of librarians in Federal Universities in Southeast, Nigeria is in tandem with allayed fear expressed by Tech Target (2024) that Like of any form can affect ethical issues and risks surrounding data privacy, security, policies and workforces and can also potentially introduce a series of new business risks like misinformation, plagiarism, copyright infringements and harmful content, lack of transparency and the potential for worker displacement as well as that of Gasparini and Kautonen (2022) who also in their study discovered a range of viewpoints among libraries and librarians towards AI, with some welcoming the technology and others worried about its potential to undermine human values and also exposed crucial challenges like ethical transparency and the place of AI as a standalone entity.

However the finding of this study is contrary to that of Yoon et al. (2022) who conducted a survey to learn about the opinions of North American librarians regarding the use of AI and associated technologies in libraries and found favourable perception of these technologies among academic and public librarians and also discovered, that 21% of librarians were already utilizing AI and related

technologies and showed intense curiosity about these technologies and similar perspectives on whether AI is appropriate for various library tasks. In all the federal university libraries in Southeast Nigeria studied, none was observed utilizing any of the AI tools let alone full application neither was there any plan to implement same within the shortest possible time.

Regardless of the perception of librarians in federal universities in Southeast Nigeria, the study found that they see AI as an asset towards enhancing library services and information delivery and dissemination. The study revealed that the librarians agree that AI can be used to develop personalized recommendation systems that suggest relevant materials based on user preference and behavior, Use of AI will promote digital preservation and archiving, It will enhance information accessibility as AI and robotics will make library services more accessible for both able and disabled individuals, including text-to-speech, sign language interpretation and navigation assistance., Exploring the role of AI-powered Chatbots and virtual assistants will enhance the provision of instant customer support, answering queries and assisting with information retrieval, Utilizing AI-driven data analytics to assess user trends, preference and demands, thereby informing collection development strategies and that Robots can be used to perform library technical jobs like classification, shelving and selection of information materials among others.

This result is an affirmation of the findings of Panda and Chakravarty (2022) in a study through the utilization of Engati, a versatile AI chatbot service, to provide an overview of its uses and multitasking features in libraries found that AI chatbots offer a reliable solution for initiating virtual assistance, augmenting reference services, and promoting a "library without walls" concept as well as that of Huang (2022) who in a study on the applications of AI in Taiwanese university libraries revealed that the librarians' had positive views towards the use of AI but require more in-depth information and organizational activities surrounding AI.

5.0. Conclusion and recommendations

The result of this study is an expository as it has thrown open how knowledgeable librarians in federal universities in southeast are of AI and its tools. The result shows a very low level of awareness of AI tools regardless of the fact that they are very knowledgeable of

AI applications, robotics and robots as well as ChatGPT and generative AI (see table 1). It also brings at bay the allayed fears of librarians though not peculiar to librarians in federal universities in Nigeria rather a global challenge associated with AI applications and utilization. The outcome further shows that librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria despite their negative perception of AI as a result of the fear of the known as displayed in table 2 still have positive perception of the technology as they believe as shown in table 3 that AI applications and utilization in federal university libraries in Southeast, Nigeria in so any ways can enhance the library management and effective service delivery. The deduction therefore is that inasmuch as librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria are aware of the use of AI in university libraries worldwide, the universities and library management are not yet wholly prepared to incorporate the technology into their daily operations.

In all, man by nature is allergic to change but the fact remains that in life the only thing that is constant is change and in a dynamic world, man must ever be prepared for change and when it comes to any transformation relating to information, libraries especially university libraries as research hub must be at the forefront. Suffice it to say, that the spread of Artificial Intelligence certainly brings with it a combination of exciting opportunity and change. With forethought, planning, and consideration of the risks, libraries can ensure they are not only prepared for the changes that AI will bring but they are positioned to shape and then lead the world that AI is helping to create. In this regard, the following recommendations are put forward:

- Librarians in federal universities in Southeast Nigeria and by extension, federal universities in Nigeria should discard the allayed fears and view AI from the angle that it is a vital tool for the provision of vital information or knowledge in line with the transformation agenda of the global sustainable development goals (SDGs) therefore must be harnessed to its fullest. In that the combination of AI and library and information science will be in sync with delivery on development of information for sustainable development as by so doing both will become public institutions and development agents.

- No matter the way it is look at, research has shown that AI is an asset to libraries and librarians thus librarians have significant role to play as AI can also play critical role in helping librarians make key decisions that will impact the future of the library. With this technology continuing to become more prevalent, librarians are also required to educate library users on Artificial Intelligence, and how it can enhance their daily life. This implies that librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria in particular and Nigeria in general should not wait to be reminded to now tailor their efforts towards acquiring AI skills by training and retraining as to be prepared to face the challenges when the technology is finally introduced in their libraries and also to remain relevant in the scheme of things.
- As a follow up to the above, resolving the moral dilemma associated with job loss inasmuch as it requires strong policy frameworks and regulatory actions that call for governments, industry stakeholders, and academia to work together to create policies like re-skilling programs, tests with universal basic income, and ethical criteria for AI deployment, a well trained librarians with perfect AI skills need fear no fall. So the advice to librarians in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria is embark on self sponsored training, retraining and retraining as there are many online courses now on AI and machine learning (ML) that are beneficiary to librarians.
- The concern that increased use of AI could lead to the spread of disinformation and misinformation, not to mention security and privacy issues. Librarians can play a pivotal role in championing the responsible use of AI and must learn how to discern AI-generated text and images to pass these skills on to users and this can only be achieved when librarians are well trained and retrained. The bulk is therefore on the librarians table to utilize every opportunity offered by AI as by so doing both the libraries and librarians will be best for it.
- The federal government on their part should through proper financing and policies formulation relating to the use of AI ensure the application and utilization of AI in federal university libraries as the taste of the pudgy is in the eating. With this, the federal university libraries will not be left behind in emerging global computer driven technologies like the AI as that is the only way they can share and gain from global information hub and development.

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